

Synthesis and Ring Expansion of some 2-Azabicyclo[4.4.0]decan-5-ones

N. BHAVANI* and D. NATARAJAN

Department of Chemistry, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002

Manuscript received 31 December 1991, revised 23 December 1992, accepted 7 January 1993

The stereoisomeric forms of many pharmacologically active morphine derivatives differ greatly in their analgesic potency^{1,2}. Hexahydro-1,4-diazepin-5-ones (1)³, 5,7-benzomorphans (2)⁴ and a variety of 4-phenylpiperidine (3)⁵ derivatives have useful pharmacological properties.

We were involved in the exploration of the stereochemistry of these type of molecules. In this connection we synthesised some diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undecanones by employing Schmidt reaction and determined the migratory nature during the rearrangement.

Compounds 5a—e were prepared in 20—25% yields following a reported procedure⁶. The ketones (5a, b) were characterised by nmr, ir and microanalytical data.

- 4, 5a; R = C₂H₅, R' = H, Ar = Ph
 b; R = R' = CH₃, Ar = Ph
 c; R = CH₃, R' = H, Ar = Ph
 d; R = R' = H, Ar = Ph
 e; R = R' = H, Ar = *p*-Cl C₆H₄

The ring expansion of cyclic ketones is frequently complicated by the problem of closely similar α - and α' -migrating aptitudes leading to two isomeric ring-expanded products. This problem is critical in the case of unsymmetrical cyclohexanones and 3-ketosteroids⁷. Five 2-azabicyclo[4.4.0]decan-5-ones (5a—e) were subjected to ring expansion

through Schmidt reaction. Since the ketones are unsymmetrical, two ring-expanded products (6 or 7) are possible depending on whether the ring-fusion carbon or the other adjacent carbon undergoes migration.

In case of all the ring-expanded products prepared, only a single isomer was isolated as shown by tlc. Compounds 5d and 5e without substituent at C₄ gave 2,6-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undecan-5-ones (7d and 7e) while 5a—c with one or two alkyl substituents at C₄ gave 2,5-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undecan-6-ones (6a—c). The structures of the compounds were confirmed by carrying out acid hydrolysis and identifying the product formed. Hydrolysis of product 7d gave cinnamic acid 7e *p*-chlorocinnamic acid and 1,2-diaminocyclohexane, but 6a—c on hydrolysis gave cyclohexenecarboxylic acid and an acyclic 1,2-diamine. From the hydrolysis products it is clear that when there is an alkyl substituent in the α -position to the carbonyl group, this carbon undergoes migration to give product 6⁸; but for ketones without a substituent at α -position to carbonyl group, ring fusion carbon undergoes migration to give product 7.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco IR 700 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Jeol GSX-400 FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

4-Ethyl-3-phenyl-2-azabicyclo[4.4.0]decan-5-one (5a): A mixture of Δ^1 -butanoylcyclohexene (0.1 mol), benzaldehyde (0.1 mol), dry ammonium acetate (0.12 mol), ethanol (20 ml) and piperidine

(3 drops) was refluxed for 2–3 h. To the resulting cooled solution, ether (200 ml) was added, followed by concentrated HCl (20 ml). The mixture was then stirred well and allowed to stand for 1 h. The precipitated hydrochloride was washed with ethanol-ether (1 : 5) mixture to remove coloured impurities. The base was liberated by suspending the hydrochloride in acetone and strong ammonia was added till the solid disappeared. Dilution with water afforded the base. The separated solid was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to give 5a as colourless crystals, m.p. 61–62° (Found: C, 78.9; H, 9.4. $C_{17}H_{23}NO$ calcd. for: C, 79.4; H, 9.0%); ν_{\max} 1 698 (C=O) and 3 316 cm^{-1} (NH); δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.74 (3H, t, J 7.3 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 0.95–1.07 (1H, m, CH_2CH_3), 1.58–1.63 (1H, m, CH_2CH_3), 1.63 (1H, s, NH), 2.23–2.32 (1H, m, C_6-H), 2.52–2.63 (2H, m, C_1-H and C_4-H), 3.63 (1H, d, C_2-H), 7.28 (5H, ArH), 1.7–1.87 (3H, m) and 1.2–1.58 (5H, m, CH_2 of cyclohexane ring protons).

Other compounds (5b–e) were prepared in a similar manner: 5b, m.p. 116–17° (EtOH) (Found: C, 79.3; H, 9.1. $C_{17}H_{23}NO$ calcd. for: C, 79.3; H, 8.9%); ν_{\max} 1 696 (C=O) and 3 312 cm^{-1} (NH); δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (3H, s, CH_3 at C_4), 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3 at C_4), 1.59 (1H, s, NH), 2.4–2.58 (2H, m, C_1-H and C_6-H), 3.7 (1H, s, C_3-H), 7.25 (5H, ArH), 1.2–1.35 (4H, m) and 1.74–1.95 (4H, m, CH_2 of cyclohexane ring protons); 5c, 130–31°; 5d, 99–100°; 5e, 136–37°. Baliah and Natarajan⁶ reported the same melting point for the three compounds.

Schmidt reaction of the ketones (5a–e): The reported procedure⁹ for the synthesis of homopiperazin-5-ones was slightly modified. The appropriate bicyclic ketone hydrochloride (0.01 mol) was dissolved in concentrated H_2SO_4 (25 ml). Sodium azide (0.025 mol) was added to it in small portions with constant stirring during a period of 1 h. The stirring was continued for another hour. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice and was neutralised with ice-cold NaOH solution. The separated solid was dried and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to give 6a–c and 7d, 7e: 6a (76%), m.p. 121–22°; ν_{\max} 1 658

(C=O), 3 420 (NH); 6b (84%), m.p. 195–96°; ν_{\max} 1 656, 3 446; 6c (73%), 161–62°; ν_{\max} 1 654, 3 446; 7d (81%), 177–78°; ν_{\max} 1 654, 3 440; 7e (79%), 213–14°; ν_{\max} 1 656, 3 446 cm^{-1} .

Acid hydrolysis⁸ of the lactams (6 and 7). General procedure: The lactam (7d; 0.5 g) was dissolved in 6N HCl (20 ml) and the solution refluxed for 4 h. On cooling it overnight, a solid separated which was identified as cinnamic acid. Again the solution was refluxed for 4 h and the cinnamic acid was removed after cooling. The solution was then extracted with ether to remove the dissolved cinnamic acid and evaporated on a steam-bath. The 1,2-ethanediamine was obtained as dihydrochloride. In the case of 7e, the reaction mixture was kept in a refrigerator to obtain *p*-chlorocinnamic acid. From the hydrolysis of 6a–c an oily substance was obtained in each case, which was identified as cyclohexenecarboxylic acid (ν_{\max} 1 687 (C=O) and \sim 3 300 cm^{-1} (OH)).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for microanalysis and to the Annamalai University for the award of a studentship to one of them (D. N.). The authors wish to express their thanks to Professor R. Jeyaraman, Bharathidasan University, Trichy, for his helpful discussion.

References

1. N. B. EDDY and E. L. MAY, "Synthetic Analgesics", Pergamon, Oxford, 1966, Part IIB.
2. A. H. BECKETT and A. F. CASY, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1954, 6, 986.
3. R. SEKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Annamalai University, 1983.
4. A. F. CASY and A. P. PARULKAR, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, 47, 3623.
5. A. F. CASY, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 22, 2711; *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1966, 1157; *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 188.
6. V. BALIAH and A. NATARAJAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 830.
7. V. DAVE, J. B. STOTHERS and E. W. WARNHOFF, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, 57, 1557.
8. V. BALIAH, MR. LAKSHMANAN and K. PANDIARAJAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 16, 72.
9. T. RENGARAJAN, K. PANDIARAJAN and J. CHELLAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 778.